

Challenges in Career – Third House

26 Comments / English Blogs / By Deepanshu Giri

The third house helps us communicate with the world, The way we express ourselves and it is not only about speech but overall posture, personality and aura we carry around us before even a person opens his mouth his personality communicates a lot, People fall in love with your personality not with looks, as you can look gorgeous but your shitty attitude will drive everyone away or make you popular amongst the masses.

The third house is the news and always remember bad news spreads fast as this is what everyone wants to consume and feel happy about, this tells us a lot of the nature of Humans that when someone speaks ill of another person, we feel satisfied and share the news next moment to anyone else while Good news is something we keep up to ourselves as there is no fun in spreading good deeds of any person.

When people say I am in struggling in business, no one wants to promote, work with me or even give credit for my work, This is because you have spoiled your third house- The third house is 6th from the 10th house which shows challenges in work and profession, A man who is not proud of his profession

is a miserable person who is not happy with himself and to bring others down the best and easy tasks someone finds is drag everyone else down by throwing shit others which one has accumulated over a period of time by listening to others.

The third house is one of the input senses and you should be very careful about what information you are collecting from everyone – Is it someone else shit or something useful – One of the books I was reading on Rebel Kings of India – Story is narrated when someone was bad mouthing Maharana Pratap in front of Akbar- Akbar ordered that person to be thrown in Jail and when courtier asked the reason as Rana was enemy of Mughal Empire ” What wrong have I done Jahapanah ?”

Akbar replied, “To even talk about Rana you need some courage and the words you chose to demean him show your inability to even understand the greatness of Maharana, you need to first learn the courage which Rana Ji has.” What a great King Akbar was! You can say anything to him but this gesture was something we need to learn from, Two kings fighting like Kings.

I think that is why the Late Rahat Indori Ji wrote

“सिर्फ खंजर ही नहीं, आंखों में भी पानी चाहिए, ऐ खुदा...मुझे दुश्मन भी खानदानी चाहिए.”

Most People are like courtiers in Akbar's court and that is why when you see people who have a number of challenges in careers have spoiled third house by their own actions as instead of addressing their own insecurities and shortcomings, they try to bring others down by telling lies, spreading wrong news and mocking someone who is way bigger than them, It's like criticising Government on how to run a country when a same person is not even able to handle his own house.

The third lord when conjoined with malefics placed in 6/8/12 or placed alone and respected by malefics natives had a bad influence on the environment around which programs them for failure and misery in life, When 3rd lord is with Venus/Jupiter/Moon/Mercury- native get positive friends with a lot of good ideas and environment is about how we can solve the problem, help each create an environment where everyone can grow, Good position of 3rd lord ensure to create and give all the necessary tools, equipment and people which will then create an environment where you will continuously grow as one friend will take care of fighting, one will take care finance and by mutual understanding, you have the environment to prosper.

Some of the remedies to remove the obstacles from a career are –

- 1) Learn to read at least 1 book a week on various subjects from History to Self-help as books program your brain to give deep ideas.
- 2) Whenever you hear/read or come across a person who is glorifying himself by downsizing others- Smile and move away to block that person from the group or clearly state I am not interested in this let us talk about something positive as sometimes within our own house/family/friends gossip about others.

3) Every morning when you wake up Sit down for 2 mins watch your hands and pray " Let me be useful for others today." – Have trust in your efforts and keep doing the best of your work with passion.

4) Every day carefully analyse your surroundings, If you see something negative like broken glasses, sound indoors, blocked windows, or A fearful painting, replace it with an appealing view.

5) Learn to appreciate others even in the smallest of gestures, the most important is while driving, Learn patience- When you drive on the road you will find everyone like life on a trip- Some good, some bad, some horrible drivers while you might be waiting patiently in line someone will cut through using the wrong lane, Let them go early as they are slaves and if they don't reach on time, they will be punished.

6) Offering flowers for 24 days in the temple.

Let me tell you something- People who are in a hurry are thinking that by reaching 10 mins early they will achieve something but it is always the slave mentality to reach anywhere in a hurry, When you live with the master mentality you drive at your own pace singing along.

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